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A Study on the Occupational Safety and Health in Perspective of Disaster Management Approach: Research on Ready-Made Garments Sector of Bangladesh

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Accepted: 12 November, 2019; **Online:** 17 November, 2019

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3545009>

Abstract: During the last three decades' workplace safety has emerged as an area of major concern for employers as well as employees. This research focuses the present scenario of occupational safety and health in Readymade Garments (RMG) sector of Bangladesh, the achievement of Accord, Alliance and National Tripartite Plan of Action (NTPA) after Rana Plaza accident. Primary data collected through Key Informant Interviews (KII) with garment workers, managers, safety committee members, fire service civil defense official, development agency like World Bank and UN professionals. Secondary data collected through the review of literature on the study related to occupational health & safety, workplace safety, legal settings, sustainability compact studies and by reviewing recent published and unpublished materials. The study shows that 6 years after the establishment of the Accord, more than 1600 of its enlisted factories has completed 90% of their initial remediation works among which 227 factories has done all of their suggested remediation works. On the other hand, 428 members factories of the Alliance of North American brands led initiative has completed all items identified in their initial reports before ceasing their activities in Bangladesh and under the national initiative from the Bangladesh Government, it's members have completed 30% remediation work. The study also reveals that Accord field activities including verifying the remediation works and its workplace safety programs are more transparent than the others. Key informants of this study have appreciated the present development of the Accord and alliances as well as they have criticized different relevant issues which may have negative effect on the achievement on both platforms. With the efforts of the Accord and Alliance significant development in the workplace safety have achieved but still more work needs to be done. There also lies a big challenge for smooth transition of these external organizations to carry over their future works by the local bodies with transparency, rigorous, readiness and well enforcement.

Keywords: Workplace Safety, OSH, Disaster Management, RMG, ACCORD, Alliance, Bangladesh

Introduction

At present occupational hazard lies as the hazardous genesis of almost all fatalities in this digital and industrialized generation. The reason behind this statement came from the statistics estimated by the International Labor Organization (ILO) according to which, from over the 2.3 million fatalities that take place annually, over 2 million fatalities are caused by work related diseases. Safe work is one of the principal privileges of the laborers.

It is evaluated that all around 160 million individuals are influenced by avoidable work related sicknesses and the sky is the limit from there than two million laborers kick the bucket from business related mischances every year (Kwame, Kusi et al. 2014). Also, businesses confront expensive early retirements, loss of gifted staff, truancy, and high protection premiums because of business related mischances and ailments. Behind these mentioned reasons, during the last three decades workplace safety has emerged as an area of major concern for employers as well as employees.

The Bangladesh RMG industry is one of the most thriving industry in the world but still there are lots of problems prevailing that needs to be resolved in order to gain sustainability. Productivity, working conditions, low value-addition and low flexibility are some of the major problems that exists in the industry. These complications need comprehensive research and innovation so that the solutions can endow benefits to the mass level factories. The practice of Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) and ergonomics in the RMG industries are still not up to the mark and most of the top management considers them as a burden towards profitability.

Background

There are 57.6 million workforces working in Bangladesh as per the latest official statistics. According to Bangladesh Institute of Labor Studies (BILS) information, only 20% percent of the total workforce enjoy privileges stipulated in the Labor Law. Even the rights of the workers covered by the law are not fully implemented.

The readymade garment industry of Bangladesh has very significant contributions to the country's economic development in terms of foreign earnings, employment opportunities, women empowerment and bringing social change. The contribution of Bangladesh's ready-made garment industry in the world apparel sector is very significant, currently it has become the

2nd largest exporters of garment products in the world. Bangladesh is the second largest apparel exporter worldwide after China, Bangladesh exported garment items worth \$28.14 billion in the last fiscal year, registering 0.20 percent year-on-year growth (Textile Today, 2017). More than 4 million workers invest their labors in the sector (Kaniz Farhana, Md. Syduzzaman, 2015).

Workplace safety is one of the most important issues in industries worldwide and is endangered by industrial accidents. Different industrial disasters have resulted in several initiatives worldwide to protect human life and reduce material damage, both nationally and internationally. In Bangladesh, the ready-made garment (RMG) industry is one of the most important export-oriented business sectors, which is facing challenges to ensure workplace safety. The Rana Plaza collapse in Bangladesh is the consequence of such non-compliance. The accident resulted in different local and global initiatives to address the challenges. This article reviews progress and achievement of the initiatives to reduce vulnerability in the Bangladesh RMG industry within 3 years after the deadly accident. In the long run, the challenge is to maintain momentum already created for achieving sustainability in the RMG sector in Bangladesh and maintaining compliance even after the end of support from external partners (Barua and Mehedi Ansary, 2016).

Objectives

The research focuses on the following objectives for reviewing the sectoral assessment of occupational health and safety in perspective of disaster management approaches in the RMG sector of Bangladesh.

- To find out the overall status of occupational health and safety status in RMG of Bangladesh
- To evaluate the linkage between Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) and Disaster Management (DM)

Data and Methods

This research is based on both primary data and secondary data, while secondary data include publicly disclosure materials, published reports, working papers, news articles with an intensive literature review. Primary data were collected through Key Informant Interviews with Safety Committee members (Managers and Workers), garment owner, Bangladesh Fire Service and Civil Defense (FSCD) officials and development agency officials. In doing so, firstly a conceptual understanding of research problem and theoretical framework and then analyzing and

identifying the status of occupational health and safety, assessing of the OSH components, comparative analysis of OSH issues after Rana plaza, Tazreen fashion disaster. The collected data from relevant stakeholders organized and processed. Finally, the key informants' comments are embedded in the result and recommendation phase.

Occupational Safety and Health (OSH):

Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) is generally defined as the science of the anticipation, recognition, evaluation and control of hazards arising in the workplace that could impair the health and well-being of workers, taking into account the possible impact on the surrounding communities and the general environment. This domain is necessarily vast, encompassing many disciplines and numerous workplace and environmental hazards. A wide range of structures, skills, knowledge and analytical capacities are needed to coordinate and implement all the “building blocks” that make up national OSH systems so that protection is extended to both workers and the environment. The scope of occupational safety and health has evolved gradually and continuously in response to social, political, technological and economic changes. In recent years, globalization of the world's economies and its repercussions have been perceived as the greatest force for change in the world of work, and consequently in the scope of occupational safety and health, in both positive and negative ways. Liberalization of world trade, rapid technological progress, significant developments in transport and communication, shifting patterns of employment, changes in work organization practices, the different employment patterns of men and women, and the size, structure and life cycles of enterprises and of new technologies can all generate new types and patterns of hazards, exposures and risks. Demographic changes and population movements, and the consequent pressures on the global environment can also affect safety and health in the world of work (Fundamental principles of occupational health and safety, Benjamin O, ILO).

Occupational Health and Safety is a holistic approach towards total wellbeing of the employee at work. According to WHO (1995), occupational health includes the actions for occupational medicine, occupational hygiene, occupational psychology, safety, physiotherapy, ergonomics, rehabilitation, etc. Safety on the other side involves the protection of people from physical injury (Hughes et al, 2008). The International Occupational Hygiene Association (IOHA) generally defines occupational health and safety (OHS) as the science of anticipation, recognition, evaluation and control of hazards arising in or from the workplace that could impair the health

and well-being of workers, taking into account the possible impact on the surrounding communities and the general environment (ILO, 2009). Thus, OHS can be seen to concern the promotion and maintenance of the highest degree of physical, mental and social well-being of workers in all occupations (ILO/WHO, 1995)

Box-1: Safety and Health at Work – A Human Right

The right to safety and health at work is enshrined in the **United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948**, which states:

Everyone has the right to work, to free choice of employment, to just and favorable conditions of work ... (Article 23)

The United Nations International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, 1976, reaffirms this right in the following terms:

The States Parties to the present Covenant recognize the right of everyone to the enjoyment of just and favorable conditions of work, which ensure, in particular: ... (b) Safe and healthy working conditions ... (Article 7)

Safety & Health Hazards & Different Forms

A hazard is a potential for harm (physical or mental). In practical terms, a hazard is often associated with a condition or activity that, if left uncontrolled, can result in an injury or illness. Identifying hazards and eliminating or controlling them as early as possible will help prevent injuries and illnesses (OSHA, US Department of Labor)

Common Hazards in RMG of Bangladesh

Basically, RMG factories have the huge inclusion of different complex safety and health hazards. Hazards are the common phenomenon of everyday life in Bangladesh garments sector. Everyday anyone of the workers can face these hazards. There are many hazards categories exist in garments industries i.e. mechanical, electrical, fire induced, structural, chemical, biological, ergonomic and physiological hazards.

In the broadcategory, the hazards of RMG factories are divided into 4 categories Such as

- Fire induced hazards
- Electrical hazards
- Buildings/ Structural hazards
- Others safety hazards

Fire Hazards

The rapid and unplanned clustered growth of industries leads to adverse fire hazard and environmental consequence at an alarming rate. Last few years several few devastating fire incidents have occurred with a remarkable number of deaths of the worker. This situation made the sector questionable (Md. Morshadul Hasan, Appel Mahmud).

The Accord and alliance initial inspection and follow up publicly disclosure reports finds explicit causes that increases risk of fire hazards in the factory are following:

- Aisle/ Passage/ Stair blockage
- Collapsible (Kechi) gates
- Inadequate egress
- Combustible materials stored adjacent to heated areas (Generator, Boiler, Electrical Sub-station machine)
- Faulty electrical connections
- Lack of fire drill/ evacuation training
- Smoking stuffs like cigarettes, lighter, matches
- Poor natural and artificial lighting system.
- Faded marking of exit places
- Improper House keeping
- Dust inside DB/SDB board
- Boiler blast
- Generator explosion
- Chemical explosion

Electrical Hazards

Electrical hazards are also main source of fire in the factory. The two most basic risks from electricity are electrical shocks, which can seriously harm or execute, and the likelihood of flames caused by electrical short-circuits.

A list of common electrical hazards are following from Accord and Alliance Initial Inspection, follow up publicly disclosure reports:

- Improper Grounding
- Exposed Electrical Parts

- Damaged Insulation
- Overloaded Circuits
- Damaged Tools & Equipment
- Wet Conditions in power station
- Overhead Power Lines
- Joint & uncovered electrical wire
- Dust on electrical line & equipment's
- Live wire on the production floor
- Burned socket or switch

Building/Structural Hazards:

Building collapse is one of the major risks factors for readymade garments industry. The major reason for building collapses are- the foundations are too weak, the building materials aren't strong enough, Workers make mistake, the load is heavier than expected and the strength is not tested [BBC, 2016].

The following features are reported as building hazards or structural hazards in RMG Factories. The hazards are listed from **Accord and Alliance Initial Inspection, follow up publicly disclosure reports:**

- Low quality materials used in the building
- Crack in Wall, Pillar, Beam, Roof
- Improper planned building
- Overloading issues
- Corrosion (for steel structure building)
- Unauthorized extension of main building
- Falling hazards in roof

Rana plaza building collapse on 24 April 2013. The search for the dead ended on 13 May 2013 with a death toll of 1,129. Approximately 2,500 injured people were rescued from the building alive. It is considered the deadliest garment-factory accident in history, as well as the deadliest accidental structural failure in modern human history (The Daily Observer, 2018)

Safety and Labor Standard in Bangladesh RMG Factories

The fire broke out in Tazreen Fashion and building collapse of Rana Plaza two most tragic events in the industrial history and of course it created the global attention of different stakeholders like brands, retailers and international Labor parties. In reflection various pragmatic steps implemented at the national and international level to make sure the safer workplace in RMG industry of Bangladesh. The agreements connection with three building blocks such as i) occupational safety and health standards; ii) workers' participation, unionization and collective bargaining; and iii) Labor standards. Basically, the agreement focuses on fire including electrical and structural safety in that case the initiatives was started to achieve specific safety measures in a binding manner. The salient features of these international agreements are unprecedented collective action of trade unions, brands and their supplier factories and the Labor Organization.

International Agreements:

Basically, three agreements adopted at the international level are multi-stakeholder or tripartite initiatives, involving different actors, transnational corporations, national firms, the Governments of Bangladesh and its institutions, the ILO as an international agency, global and national trade unions and other civil society organizations and campaigns. Among them, the Accord is unique as it is the first and only one that is legally binding.

ACCORD:

The Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh¹ is a legally binding agreement signed in May 2013 between more than 220 apparel corporations from more than 20 countries in Europe, North America, Asia and Australia, two international trade unions IndustriALL and UNI Global Union and seven Bangladeshi trade unions to improve safety and working conditions in the RMG industry. International NGOs and civil society campaigns based on Labor and consumer solidarity, such as Clean Clothes Campaign (CCC), International Labor Rights Forum (ILRF), Worker Rights Consortium (WRC) and Maquila Solidarity Network (MSN) are witnesses to the agreement. The International Labor Organization (ILO) acts as the independent chair of the agreement. The signatories of the agreement are obliged to establish fire and building safety through safety inspections, remediation and extensive fire safety training for a period of five years.

¹ About Accord 2013, Bangladesh Accord Website, viewed on 25 November 2018

<<http://bangladeshaccord.org/wp-content/uploads/2013-Accord-full-text.pdf>>

The agreement consists of six building blocks:

1. A five year legally binding agreement between brands and trade unions to ensure a safe working environment in the Bangladeshi RMG industry
2. An independent inspection program supported by brands in which workers and trade unions are involved
3. Public disclosure of all factories, inspection reports and corrective action plans (CAP)
4. A commitment by signatory brands to ensure enough funds are available for remediation and to maintain sourcing relationships
5. Democratically elected health and safety committees in all factories to identify and act on health and safety risks
6. Worker empowerment through an extensive training program, complaints mechanism and right to refuse unsafe work.

2018 ACCORD:

The 2018 Accord² is an independent, legally binding agreement between global brands and IndustriALL Global Union and UNI Global Union designed to work towards a safe and healthy garment Industry in Bangladesh. The 2018 Accord builds on the preceding Accord that was signed in May 2013 and is due to expire in May 2018. The signatories to the 2018 Accord agree to continue a fire and building safety program in Bangladesh to enable a working environment in which no worker needs to fear fire, building collapses or other accidents that could be prevented with reasonable health and safety measures.

The Accord signatories aim to transition the 2018 Accord functions to a national regulatory body when such a body is ready. As such the 2018 Accord will be known as the 'Transition Accord'.

Currently, 190 global apparel companies and apparel retailers have signed the 2018 Transition Accord.

Key new elements of the 2018 Accord include

- Safety committee and safety training in all covered factories
- Training and complaints protocol to cover Freedom of Association (FoA) protections in relation to workers protecting their own safety under the scope of the Transition Accord. Workers' severance payments in Accord related factory closures and relocations;

² Transitional Accord 2018, Bangladesh Accord Website, viewed on 25 November 2018

- Potential, voluntary expansion of scope to related industries;
- Transition of Accord functions to a national regulatory body when such body is ready. Release of brand responsibility for inactive factories after 18 months.
- Conditional possibility for signatories who stop sourcing from Bangladesh to terminate agreement.

RMG Sustainability Council: Accord Reaches Resolution on Continuation³:

On 19 May 2019, the Accord presented a memorandum of understanding (MoU) to the Appellate Court in Bangladesh in relation to the High Court order which would have closed the Accord Bangladesh office operations. The MoU was reached by the Accord Steering Committee and the BGMEA and has the endorsement of the Government of Bangladesh. The MoU has been accepted by the Appellate Court and will result in the 2018 Transition Accord and Accord Bangladesh office and operations continuing in Bangladesh for 281 working days. The MoU will lead to the establishment of a national RMG safety entity to be called the RMG Sustainability Council (RSC). After the transition period of 281 working days, the RSC will take over all Accord Bangladesh operations and will inherit the Accord infrastructure and staff. The RSC will be governed by a structure consisting of representatives of the BGMEA, global brands, and global and national trade unions. The RSC will work in cooperation with the Government of Bangladesh (GoB) to ensure the work of the RSC compliments the work of the GoB Remediation Coordination Cell. Over the course of this year, the Accord will work intensively with the BGMEA so that they gain an intimate knowledge of the Accord's day-to-day work, operations, systems, protocols, data management, and disclosure related to the core functions of the Accord: inspections & remediation, safety training, safety complaint resolution, and public reporting.

A BGMEA team consisting of a technical officer and an engineer will be assigned to work with the Accord Bangladesh office to ensure this knowledge and full understanding of the Accord operations is transferred. Also, over the course of the next year, the BGMEA and Accord Steering Committee will finalize the practical details related to the establishment and functioning of the RSC. Through the MoU, all operations, staff, infrastructure and functions of the Accord

³ Accord Reaches Resolution on Continuation of Its Work in Bangladesh, Bangladesh Accord Website, Viewed on 02 June 2, 2019

will continue. All existing transparency features of the Accord will also be maintained, including full disclosure of all results of inspection and remediation activities on a public website.

Accord Steering Committee brand representatives state: “establishing this national industry / Labor private initiative will make the past Accord achievement sustainable, establishing a local increased health & safety awareness and preserving the ability of the global brands and retailers to continue.

After the transition, the RSC will continue with factory inspections, remediation, follow up inspections, worker training, and the independent grievance mechanism, thus providing brands, trade unions and consumers with the necessary assurance that the vital elements of the Accord’s groundbreaking safety program will be preserved.

Importantly, all existing transparency features of the Accord will be maintained, including full disclosure of all results of inspection and remediation activities on a public website.

UNI General Secretary Christy Hoffman⁴ said:

“The agreement between the Accord and the BGMEA is an important step forward in keeping worker safety at the forefront of the Bangladesh RMG industry. The lifesaving work of the Accord can continue.”

Other than settling for an earlier exit from Bangladesh, the platform agreed to work with the Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association for the RMG Sustainability Council (RSC), a garment factory safety entity formed by the sector’s apex trade body with representation from the brands and global and national trade unions. The RSC will take over the Accord’s operations and inherit the infrastructure and staff. It will work in cooperation with the government to ensure that its work compliments that of the Remediation Coordination Cell, an entity under the Labor and employment ministry that will eventually be responsible for ensuring workplace safety in Bangladesh’s garment factories. (The Daily Star, 2019)

ALLIANCE:

The Alliance for Bangladesh Workers’ Safety is an agreement for a period of five years between 26 major North American apparel companies, retailers and brands with the intention of significantly improving workplace safety in more than 580 RMG factories from which they

⁴ Bangladesh Accord achievements secured, IndustriAll Website, Viewed on 02 June 2, 2019

source products. BRAC, a leading development NGO originating from Bangladesh, and some other US and Canadian company federations are the supporting associations of the Alliance (Alliance, 2014).

The Alliance aims to achieve its goal of a safer RMG industry in Bangladesh by focusing efforts in through five strategic pillars: Standards & Inspections, Remediation, Worker Empowerment, Training, and Sustainability.

NIRAPON in replacement of ALLIANCE:

A new self-regulating platform has emerged to oversee building inspection and remediation of listed apparel factories in Bangladesh in place of Alliance, which had been providing safety monitoring, oversight and reporting services for the North American brands and buyers.

Nirapon is committed to helping the factories from which its members source develop a sustainable culture of safety; to do so, it will focus on building capacity amongst Bangladesh's assessment and training service providers. This will be accomplished by identifying service providers capable of supporting assessments, remediation, capacity building and training. Factories manufacturing for Nirapon member brands will engage assessment and training service providers from the qualified pool, while Nirapon will validate the quality of services provided and alert membership to any potential risk and issues.

Despite being global competitors, more than 20 RMG Brands have pooled their expertise and resources under the Nirapon model. "We want to help, protect and grow the safety achievements of the last five years. The unprecedented partnership that is Nirapon will help build capacity towards a locally sustainable culture of factory safety.

Nirapon will monitor the factories from which its member brands source to verify that they: 1) continue to meet the National Action Plan harmonized standards for physical safety (structural, fire, and electrical); (2) have implemented standardized training programs focused on worker safety; and (3) continue to make the helpline service, *amader kotha*, available to their factory workers. It will serve as a single point of contact between its members and the factories on these issues and will also focus on building local capacity to manage fire and building safety to sustain the investments in worker safety that have been made to date.

Alliance worked directly with factories to drive remediation and training programmes while Nirapon's role is of oversight and independent verification of safety and training compliance and to report these results to members.

State of Progress

The Accord Progress:

The Accord recognizes the extraordinary progress that has been made over the last five years to improve fire and building safety in the Bangladeshi RMG industry. The overall progress rate of remediation at the 1620 Accord-covered factories is 85%. The Accord has engaged with 2.4 million worker participants to share vital safety information in more than 1,000 factories. Because of these efforts, millions of workers now work in safer factories. Bangladesh's garment factories also benefit materially, because buyers recognize that a factory that has completed its safety work presents far fewer risks for them.

Recently published report of Center for Global Workers Rights (CGWR) of Penn State University articulated that the Accord has identified 131,953 high-risk fire, structural and electrical safety violations in its current group of 1,621 factories and corrected and verified 97,235 of these findings an average of 60 violations corrected per factory. Some 795 factories have an initial findings remediation rate of 90 per cent or higher. Some 961 factories have an initial findings remediation rate of 85 per cent or higher.

Research report of Penn State University also stated that the Accord has provided in-depth health and safety training to personnel in 846 factories and has investigated and resolved 183 worker complaints. The good practices of Accord through Safety Committee members and management such as walk-through by conducting factory inspections to identify safety hazards; respond to employee complaints and suggestions about safety and health by establishing safety complaints box and safety bulletin board; review company accident reports to learn how such accidents can be prevented; communicate about safety and health issues to workers; meet regularly, at least once every three months. If these measures are taken properly, an outstanding effect to ensure better and sustainable workplace will be visible.

In the last 5 years, the Accord⁵ has delivered a robust, high quality, transparent, inclusive system, and it has made substantial progress to achieve the safety of workers in Bangladesh's most important export industry. But the work is not yet completed and the national structure,

⁵ Sustainability Compact Meeting, European Union Website, viewed on 30 November 2018

<[http:// trade.ec.europa.eu/doclib/docs/2018/july/tradoc_157109.pdf](http://trade.ec.europa.eu/doclib/docs/2018/july/tradoc_157109.pdf) >

notwithstanding assertions to the contrary, is not yet prepared to credibly take over the work of the Accord.

Progress of Alliance:

The Fourth Annual Report of Alliance, announcing substantial factory safety improvements and the expansion of its worker training and empowerment initiatives within the past year. The data confirm that the Alliance is on track to complete nearly all Corrective Action Plans (CAPs) except for newly added and expanding factories and to transition safety monitoring operations to trusted local partners in 2018.

Highlights from the Alliance's fifth year include:

- 93 percent of remediation across Alliance-affiliated factories is complete—including 90 percent of items most critical to life safety;
- 428 factories have completed all material items in their initial Corrective Action Plans (CAPs);
- 162 non-compliant factories have been suspended from Alliance factory list;
- Nearly 1.6 million workers have been trained to protect themselves in case of a fire emergency, and the Alliance has developed local training partners to expand the training beyond Alliance-affiliated factories;
- 28,000 security guards have been trained in fire safety and emergency evacuation procedures;
- More than 1.3 million workers across 941 Alliance and non-Alliance factories have access to *amader kotha*, the Alliance's confidential worker Helpline;
- More than 1.5 million workers now have access to a 24-hour confidential worker helpline, which has been transferred to local management under *Phulki* and will soon be available to RMG factories throughout Bangladesh; and,
- 181 worker safety committees have been formed, giving workers a seat at the table with management in resolving safety issues within their factories.

The Alliance for Bangladesh Worker Safety (“Alliance”) announced in a press release on 3rd July, additional Alliance-affiliated factories completed all material components outlined in their Corrective Action Plans, bringing the total to 364. Across all Alliance factories, 90% of all required factory remediation has been completed (Alliance Fifth Annual Report, 2018).

Initiatives by the Government of Bangladesh:

The Government of Bangladesh (GoB) through its Ministry of Labor and Employment (MoLE), Ministry of Jute and Textile and other responsible authorities has taken several notable steps to improve Labor and safety standards in the RMG industry.

National Tripartite Plan of Action (NTPA):

The Government of Bangladesh and representatives of Bangladesh employers' and workers' organizations signed an integrated National Tripartite Plan of Action on Fire Safety and Structural Integrity in the garment Sector of Bangladesh (NTPA).

The National Tripartite Plan of Action on Fire Safety and Structural Integrity in the Ready-made Garment Sector in Bangladesh (NTPA) is a national agreement jointly signed by the Ministry of Labor and Employment and representatives of workers and of the owners, with the assistance of the International Labor Organization (ILO). Initially, it was developed in March 2013 as a tripartite action plan on fire safety after the fire incident at Tazreen Fashions. After the Rana Plaza collapse, the structural component was added to the action plan. The NTPA is the most ambitious initiative undertaken by the GoB and supported by the international stakeholders, which is designed to ensure, in the long run, workplaces with internationally accepted safety and health standards across the RMG sector. It consists of 25 planned activities in three areas within a stipulated timeframe between June 2013 and December 2014.

Progress of NTPA:

After the collapse of the Rana Plaza, the Accord, Alliance and National Initiative under National Tripartite Action Plan (NTPA) began in the garment industry evaluation program. Of these, 100 percent of the remediation under the national bodies have completed less than 1 percent of the factory. However, the improvement in the factory under the Accord and the Alliance of the two international alliances is much better than that.

In the relevant sources, many safety issues have been identified under the Accord and Alliance inspection in covered factories. These have been binding on remediation. In fact, due to non-completion of the reform, the both platforms already terminated business with two hundred factories. In addition, many factory remediation works are ongoing.

Factories covered by NTPA progress of 755 factories works only 30 percent, whose only 7

factories completed 100% remediation. As a result, only 0.92 percent under national bodies have completed 100 percent remediation works.

Source: July 2018, *Hundred Percent Remediated Factory in less than 1% Factory under NTPA*, *The Dainik Azadi*, Editorial Page

Occupational Health & Safety and Disaster Management:

In this stage now, we draw a linkage between OSH and DM

Table -01: Linkage between OSH and DM	
Mitigation Preventing future emergencies or minimizing their effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industrial zoning • Inspection (Credible, Institutional, Rigorous) • Fire (Fire Door, Sprinkler, Hydrant system, Smoke detector) • Electrical (Automatic circuit barker, LPS, SLD) • Structural • Remediation • Retrofitting • Fire insurance • Regular factory visits by safety committee • Commitment of factory owners for OSH prioritization • Shaping industrial policies • Enforcement • Learning from previous industrial tragedy (Rana plaza building collapse, Tazreen fashion fire)
Preparedness Preparing to handle an emergency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Posting emergency hot line number - Emergency rescue team training - Accident/life insurance - Regular fire/evacuation drill - Safety Training of factory safety committee - Safety Monitoring System <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equipment/ Machine Safety • Egress to exit safety (most vital) • Electrical/ fire safety monitoring • Evacuation mapping • Emergency medical services • First aid practices • PPE management - Announcement if found any hazards - OSH training for Mid-level managers

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complaints mechanism establishment - Communication system development - Conflict resolution between worker & manager
Response Responding safely to an emergency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evacuate from workplace on immediate effect - Instantly coordination with FSCD - Search & rescue - Sheltering victims - Give first aid or medical support as necessary <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medicine • Blood donation • Surgery • Oxygen - Psychological intervention <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Counseling - Food & incentives
Recovery Recovering from an emergency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Restoring - Rebuilding (Build Back Better) - Rehabilitation to the victims - Give accident/life insurance facility - Reinstatement to works after renovation - Proper distribution of donation & grants

Source: Developed by author

Key Informants form the Stakeholders

Key interviews taken from mainly from the experts who are closely involved in RMG and development sectors. Basically, garments owner, manager, fire service and civil defense official, development professional interviewed on research subject.

Key Findings from KIIs

- The radical development is happened last couple of years in RMG sector, right now 7 certified green factory RMG factories in Bangladesh. Many RMG factories now are well equipped in terms of health & safety. Factory have wide passageway to egress, adequate light, fire detection & protection system, enough manpower, safe drinking water, dining space etc.
- But it is true the safety changes beginning just aftermath of Rana Plaza building collapse which accelerate the establishment of Accord and Alliance.

- The two giant buyers compact started their operation in fire, electrical, structural without studying the ground as well as the socio- economic perspectives.
- If the fire service and civil defense authority took part in the compact based on their experiences that would be more convenient to establish the fire equipment's and it's maintenance
- Accord, Alliance new format RMG sustainability council and Nirapon will not continue their ongoing activities independently the sector may back in previous non-compliance condition.
- Now the responsibility goes to national authority to take over the Accord and Alliance works what they achieved in last 5-6 years with rigorousness, transparency and enforcement

Conclusion

Occupational health and safety are the foundation of wellbeing at work. The employer is responsible for providing safe working conditions, but working environment is safe only when the employees and their supervisors cooperate and participate. The aim of this guide is to provide basic information on the development of occupational safety and health in the workplace.

The aim of occupational safety and health protection measures is to prevent fatal accidents, injuries, damage to property and environmental damage within the framework of work system.

Disaster management an ongoing process and interventions by governments, corporate walls, civil society and other relevant stakeholders plans to reduce the impact of disasters, react during and immediately following a disaster, and take steps to recover after a disaster has occurred.

In RMG sector have made significant progress after two deadliest disaster but significantly behind the ultimate progress rate. It is tremendous effort by the Accord and Alliance for increasing the safety standard as a two separate legally binding platform of brands & trade unions basically the Accord. Consecutively the Accord covered factories almost 85% remediation works, and the alliance covered factories 93% remediation works. But unfortunately, factories covered by NTPA progress of 755 factories works only 30 percent, whose only 7 factories completed 100% remediation. That is absolutely threatening to national regulatory body for taking charge from Accord & Alliance after their planned tenure.

The major findings of the mentioned it is possible to recommend OSH issues within the disaster management approaches with a proper framework. Research finds delineated gaps between

disaster management act 2012 and OSH matters in the labor law 2013. Bridging the gaps is necessary to resolve the misconception, achieving goals and sustainability.

Lack of full and rigorous review by the government of structural and fire safety standards and regulations for RMG enterprises. As a result, anyone can open factories in an unfit structure except Accord and Alliance covered factories. There are still many factories which are in a building made for commercial purpose.

The recent development in Accord which reflected in signing Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) by Brands, Labor Union and BGMEA preserves the Accord operations into the future and guarantees a role for among the parties. The new body will eventually take over the entire Accord operations, functions and staff. Its governance will have the participation of the BGMEA/BKMEA, brands and global and national trade unions. The RSC will operate within the regulatory framework of the relevant Government department but will be separate from Government.

However how smooth this transition happens and how the inherited RSC performs its job with full transparency needs to be seen in future as there lies tremendous challenges from different stakeholders.

The informants are critically responded on the present status on OSH condition in RMG sector of Bangladesh which focuses on Accord, Alliance and national initiative achievement. The laps and gaps in the external platform activities. Although they emphasis the continuation by Bangladesh government of their milestone achievement if the cease activities in our country for the sake of sustainability.

Recommendations

The recommended OSH components within the disaster management approaches is may applicable for the all RMG factories to prevent and lessen the man-made disaster. If factory management, managerial staff, Safety Committee members understand disaster management approaches including the OSH components that is very effective for accelerating the OSH culture in every factory.

The conditions such as transparency, enforcement, rigorous readiness for processing agreed to prepare for future handover of Bangladesh Accord to a national regulator which was announced following a high-level in meeting in Bangladesh, between IndustriALL, Uni Global Union, brand

representatives and the BGMEA with the Bangladesh Ministers of Commerce and Labor. As a Bangladeshi my opinion if those condition not fulfilled it should not be transferred to any other parties. Now it is the big challenge of Bangladesh to take the responsibilities of Accord as well as Alliance.

In a huge number of factories covered by the Accord and Alliance practicing good safety standards in a regular basis, they are empowering & enacting the safety committees by different interventions such regular safety inspections, receiving safety complaints through safety complaints box, directly or via mobile phone, conducting health & safety survey in a yearly basis. Moreover, safety committee (SC) working to ensure factory OSH issues in priority basis.

References

Accord (2013): ‘Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh’ http://bangladeshaccord.org/wp-content/uploads/the_accord.pdf accessed on 20/06/2018

Accord (2018): ‘Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh’ <http://bangladeshaccord.org/wp-content/uploads/2018-Accord-full-text.pdf>, accessed on 22/06/2018

Accord (2018): ‘Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh’ http://bangladeshaccord.org/wp-content/uploads/Accord_Quarterly_Aggregate_Report_April_2018.pdf accessed on 22/06/2018

Accord (2018): ‘Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh’ <http://bangladeshaccord.org/2018/05/statement-issued-steering-committee-accord/> accessed on 22/06/2018

Accord (2019): Accord Factories with (CAPs and Reports), Bangladesh Accord, viewed on 23 March 2019, <<https://bangladeshaccord.org/factories>>

Alliance (2018) Alliance Delivers Significant Factory Safety Progress in Year Four, Alliance Fourth Annual Report – 2017, <http://www.bangladeshworkersafety.org/files/ALLIANCE%20THIRD%20ANNUAL%20REPORT%20OCT%202016.pdf>

Alliance (2018) Inspection Reports and CAPs, Alliance for Bangladesh Worker Safety, viewed on 14 November 2018, <<http://www.bangladeshworkersafety.org/factory/reports-caps>>

- Alli, B. O. *Fundamental principles of occupational health and safety* / Benjamin O. Alli; International Labor Office – Geneva: ILO, 2008
- Alam M.J./ Mamun, M.Z./ Islam, N. (2004): ‘Workplace Security of Female Garment Workers in Bangladesh’, *Social Science Review*, vol. 21, No. 2, pp. 191-200.**
- Ahamed, F. (2011): ‘Working Conditions in the Bangladesh Readymade Garments Industry: Is Social Compliance Making a Difference?’ PhD Thesis, La Trobe University, Australia.**
- Alam M.J./ Mamun, M.Z./ Islam, N. (2004): ‘Workplace Security of Female Garment Workers in Bangladesh’, *Social Science Review*, vol. 21, No. 2, pp. 191-200.**
- Anner, Mark, and Jennifer Bair. 2016. *The Bulk of the Iceberg: A Critique of the Stern Center’s Report on Worker Safety in Bangladesh*. State College, PA: Center for Global Workers’ Rights.
- Anner, Mark, Jennifer Bair, and Jeremy Blasi. 2013. “Toward Joint Liability in Global Supply Chains: Addressing the Root Causes of Labor Violations in International Subcontracting Networks.” *International Labor Law & Policy Journal* 35 (1): 1-43
- Bride, Michael. 2017. “Access to Remedy for Bangladeshi Readymade Garment Workers: Lessons from the Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh.” Presented at the American Bar Association Section of International Labor & Employment Law, Midyear Meeting, Dublin.
- Dannecker, P. (2000): ‘Collective Action, Organisation Building, and Leadership: Women Workers in the Garment Sector in Bangladesh’ in: *Gender and Development*, Vol 8, no 3, pp. 31-38.**
- European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, Portal to all the OSH information and legislation developed by the European Commission and the Member States of the European Union: <http://osha.europa.eu/>
- Fedotov, I.A.; Saux, M.; Rantanen, J. (eds). 1998. “Occupational health services”, in *Encyclopedia of occupational health and safety*, 4th ed., Vol. I (Geneva, ILO), pp. 161–62.
- Geref, Gary. 1994. “The Organization of Buyer-Driven Global Commodity Chains: How U.S. Retailers Shape Overseas Production Networks.” In *Commodity Chains and Global Capitalism*, eds. Gary Geref and Miguel Korzeniewicz. Westport: Praeger. 95-122.

Geref, Gary, and Stacey Frederick. 2010. The Global Apparel Value Chain: Trade and the Crisis. Washington, DC: The World Bank Development Research Group

IndustriALL. 2017. Bangladesh Accord's binding arbitration process scores legal win, Industriall Global Union, < <http://www.industrialunion.org/bangladesh-accords-binding-arbitration-process-scores-legal-win>>

IndustriALL. 2017. Process agreed to prepare for future handover of Bangladesh Accord to a national regulator, Industriall Global Union, <<http://www.industrialunion.org/process-agreed-to-prepare-for-future-handover-of-bangladesh-accord-to-a-national-regulator>>

Joint ILO/WHO Committee, (1995). Definition of Occupational and Safety. 12th Session of Joint ILO/WHO Committee on Occupational Health, Available: www.ilo.org/safework

Khan, Mohd Raisul Islam; Wichterich, Christa, (2015) Safety and Labor conditions: the accord and the national tripartite plan of action for the garment industry of Bangladesh, International Labor Office (ILO); Global Labor University (GLU). - Geneva: ILO

ILO – Occupational Safety, Health and the Environment (SafeWork) Access point to all the ILO activities, information and standards on OSH: <http://www.ilo.org/safework>

ILO – International Occupational Safety and Health Information Centre (CIS) Access point to free and reliable online databases on many aspects of OSH and to a network of over 100 national OSH information centers (LEGOSH, CISDOC, IPCS ICSCs, database of Occupational Exposure Limits, online Encyclopedia of Occupational Health and Safety, etc.): <http://www.ilo.org/cis>.

ILO - (2009). ILO Standards on Occupational Safety and Health: Promoting a safe and healthy working environment. International Labor Conference, 98th Session. Geneva

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